

CHILD DEVELOPMENT: ISSUES OF EDUCATION AND INCLUSION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18797230>

Abstract. *In the content of the article, broad opinions are given about the content of thoughts of thinkers in the upbringing of the child, the problems of the individual and his development in education, the role of upbringing in the maturation of the individual, inclusive education, the upbringing of the perfect generation. Detailed information is given about upbringing, the fact that it is a continuous process, that upbringing is in the highest place in a person's life, the relevance of inclusive education in current education reforms, the life skills of children and its importance in the life of a child.*

Keywords: *upbringing, personality, student, educator, science, school, teacher, inclusive education.*

INTRODUCTION

It expresses the fundamental idea of our reforms aimed at shaping the modern face of our country, establishing a democratic state and a free civil society, and creating the foundation for the third Renaissance. It is no coincidence that, based on this idea, the slogan “New Uzbekistan – towards the Third Renaissance” is being promoted in our country.

Every society, nation, and people has its own customs, morals, and codes of conduct. One of the most important duties of teachers and parents is to instill national customs, morals, and codes of conduct in future generations. Education is a continuous, uninterrupted process of psychological and pedagogical significance that cannot be delayed. In this process, the future destiny of a person, as well as the destiny of the society and system directly related to the person, can be determined. The New Uzbekistan strategy, the implementation of noble intentions, and unparalleled changes in building a new life demand from all of us dedication, creativity, and even greater devotion.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020, No. PQ-4884 “On additional measures to further improve the education system,” and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020, No. PF-6108 “On measures to develop education, upbringing, and science in the new era of Uzbekistan’s development” set out a number of reforms in the education and upbringing system. The essence of these reforms is focused on the issues of student upbringing and the development of education.

On January 28, 2022, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Decree No. 60 “On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026.” This decree was developed as a continuation of the “Action Strategy on five priority areas of development for 2017–2021.” Decree No. 60 “On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026” sets out 100 goals, among which Goal 70 is titled “Improving State Policy on Youth.” It defines the task of assisting youth in achieving spiritual, intellectual, physical, and moral development. It also sets the task of educating youth as individuals with patriotism, civic awareness, tolerance, respect for

laws, national and universal values, capable of resisting harmful influences and currents, and possessing firm beliefs and attitudes toward life. Thus, it is clear that the priority policy of our state is directly related to the life and destiny of young people. Clause 5 of the decree defines ensuring spiritual development and taking the sphere to a new level. This shows that spirituality remains relevant today and continues to be a priority in state policy. It outlines a number of tasks:

- Preserving, promoting, and developing the national values and spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people, supported by the state;
- Ensuring the continuity of spiritual upbringing in families, educational institutions, and communities;
- Developing scientifically based indicators for assessing spiritual upbringing;
- Applying interactive methods of education and upbringing to make schools true centers of spirituality, enlightenment, and culture;
- Combating ideological attacks based on national ideas, strengthening cooperation among family, school, and community, and thereby developing the skill of ensuring the continuity of spiritual upbringing.

The implementation of this decree demonstrates our efforts to educate future generations to be spiritually healthy and mature, expand the spiritual layer, which is an important indicator of society and state development, ensure the cooperation of communities and organizations in this area, and take steps to develop the spiritual image at a new stage in the Third Renaissance.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. Upbringing is a priority task in the life of the country. A country that does not sufficiently engage in the upbringing of the younger generation will not progress. After all, any society needs to produce material and spiritual wealth for growth and development. For this, the younger generation must be able to develop spiritual wealth at the level of their ancestors, or even better. Having an effective upbringing system is important for shaping such material and spiritual abilities in the younger generation. Education cannot be separated from upbringing, just as upbringing cannot be separated from education; in a rapidly developing era, upbringing must underlie education. It is appropriate for science to be conducted based on education and upbringing. Moreover, the purpose of every teacher and instructor in providing education is to nurture a generation with a bright future, serving the nation and homeland, and such education and upbringing will inevitably be effective. That is, today's teacher must educate their students with dedication and be a committed mentor.

From the above, it is evident that responsibility in upbringing always depends not only on parents but also on the efforts of skilled and scientifically capable teachers. It is important to know not only the forms of organizing work but also the proper ways to conduct it.

The most important tools in upbringing are love and gentle speech. These two tools together honor the child. Education should also not be carried out with anger or punishment. Knowledge forced upon a child is quickly forgotten, and as a result, the child may lose interest in the subject. Thus, education begins with proper upbringing and manners.

The content of modern upbringing is a combination of knowledge, skills, abilities, and qualities that learners must acquire according to set goals and tasks. The main ideas of upbringing are: upbringing goals, the relationship between the object and the subject, finding one's own path, and the educator's focus on personal and collective orientation. The content of modern upbringing consists of knowledge, skills, abilities, and qualities, which learners must acquire according to goals and tasks.

When defining the goals of upbringing, it is important to implement upbringing tasks, content, tools, forms, and methods, as well as self-upbringing. The pedagogical interaction between the educator and the learner is carried out through emotions.

Wide opportunities are being created for the younger generation to grow up fully, and many beneficial activities are being implemented. These include social protection of mothers and children, creating a healthy family environment and lifestyle, organizing children's free time properly, involving them in sports and additional education, health-improving and preventive measures, vocational guidance, and nurturing a comprehensively developed mature individual. The effectiveness of education and upbringing depends on cooperation with the family. The proper upbringing of a child and fostering their moral and spiritual development is directly related to the parents' sense of high responsibility. The content of upbringing is based on the best traditions in Uzbek families and is also reflected in the education and upbringing provided by communities, families, and educational institutions. Expected results can only be achieved when family upbringing is closely linked with social upbringing.

Thus, the role of fathers in forming healthy family relationships and raising children as mature and complete individuals is invaluable. Every person's greatest treasure in life is their children. Every parent wishes to raise their child well, realize their dreams, and achieve high goals. These wishes do not come true on their own. In such situations, parents must be extremely careful and attentive in upbringing. Only by faithfully fulfilling their duties can they achieve the intended goals.

One of the directions of development in Uzbekistan's education is the introduction of inclusive education in general education schools. Inclusive education is a system that ensures every child, including those with disabilities, developmental disorders, in need of social protection, or with other special needs, receives education on an equal basis in general education institutions. This approach is based on human rights, equality, and anti-discrimination principles.

The main goal of inclusive education is to create equal opportunities for all children, taking into account their physical, intellectual, social, and educational needs. This system fosters tolerance, unity, mutual respect, and equality in society. Inclusive education also plays an important role in ensuring children's independence, social activity, and adaptation to the labor market. In recent years, systematic reforms have been implemented in Uzbekistan to introduce inclusive education:

Legal norms have been developed for organizing inclusive education based on learners' social needs and personal interests, ensuring a strong integration of science, education, and production.

To organize inclusive education for children with special educational needs, it is necessary to strengthen the material and technical base of educational institutions, adapt curricula, expand access to quality health-improving educational services, and train highly qualified personnel for this process. Solving socio-pedagogical issues requires mutually beneficial cooperation among education, healthcare, and community organizations to provide quality educational services to children with limited abilities.

In 2020, the "Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education for 2020–2025" was adopted by presidential decree. Special teachers and psychologists were trained, and professional development courses were organized. Methodical and technical support tools for inclusive education (audio books, ramps, visual guides, etc.) are being implemented. Inclusive education today is important not only for children with special needs but for society as a whole in social,

educational, and humanitarian terms. Reforms and legal-organizational conditions in Uzbekistan in this area will create a foundation for fair and quality education for all children in the future.

Inclusive education is organized through differentiated teaching, adapted assignments, individual development plans, and tailored teaching materials. This primarily creates a favorable environment for such children and provides conditions for utilizing their abilities in various ways. A comfortable environment helps children quickly find their place in society like healthy children and become beneficial members of society. Abu Rayhan Beruni identified three factors in human perfection: environment, upbringing, and heredity. Thus, the environment plays a significant role in determining what kind of person a child will become. The comfortable environment and effective approaches created for inclusive children ensure their bright future.

In the future, every school's ability to accept children with diverse educational needs is one of the main goals of inclusive education. This not only causes changes in school structure and operations but also changes the mindset of teachers in general and special education institutions who have been accustomed to working with only certain groups of children. Modern pedagogical traditions operate based on approaches that place the learner at the center of the educational process, requiring teachers to be ready to meet the needs of all children.

CONCLUSION. In the process of pedagogical cooperation, a child forms and develops as a personality. Together with the interests, demands, aspirations, and enthusiasm of the individual and the community, they take steps toward perfection. In general, the basis of the goal of upbringing is to nurture a morally high, comprehensively developed, and patriotic individual. The management of the upbringing process plays an important role in the activities of teachers. In modern pedagogy, upbringing is not simply the educator's influence on the learner but the relationships and interactions between educators and learners directed toward a specific goal and conducted cooperatively. Today, it is not only about raising a person with knowledge but also about educating a creative, talented, and enterprising individual.

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